

Antibody Characterization Report for Serine/threonine-protein kinase PINK1

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: Serine/threonine-protein kinase PINK1

Alternative protein name: PTEN-induced putative kinase protein 1

Gene name: *PINK1*

Uniprot: Q9BXM7

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized thirteen Serine/threonine-protein kinase PINK1 commercial antibodies for Western Blot, using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. An HAP1 *PINK1* KO line is available at Horizon discovery and was used in this study.

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC000798c009	CVCL_TD86	HAP1	<i>PINK1</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Serine/threonine-protein kinase PINK1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab137361	GR117837	AB_2927725	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb
Abcam	ab186303*	GR3414175	AB_2827698	monoclonal	N4/15	mouse	1.000	Wb,IF
Abcam	ab216144**	GR3340291-6	AB_2927726	recombinant-mono	EPR20730	rabbit	0.702	Wb,IP,IF
Abcam	ab23707	GR3408052-1	AB_447627	polyclonal	-	rabbit	not provided	Wb
Abcam	ab300623**	3101002938	AB_2927727	recombinant-mono	MJF-R32-7	rabbit	0.522	Wb
ABclonal	A7131	603280301	AB_2767686	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2.640	Wb,IF
Bio-Techne	BC100-494	O-3	AB_10127658	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb,IP,IF
Bio-Techne	NBP2-36488*	A6	AB_2848201	monoclonal	8E10.1D6	mouse	1.000	Wb,IF
Cell Signaling Technology	6946**	4	AB_11179069	recombinant-mono	D8G3	rabbit	0.954	Wb,IP
Proteintech	23274-1-AP	101140	AB_2879244	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.500	Wb,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-11153*	XD3572331	AB_11005181	monoclonal	38CT18.2.6	mouse	0.500	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-13402	XD3572338	AB_2252385	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2.000	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-86941	XE3571725A	AB_2803698	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb,IF

Wb=Western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 1: Serine/threonine-protein kinase PINK1 antibody screening by Western Blot.

HAP1 WT and *PINK1* KO were treated with 10 μ M of CCCP (Carbonyl cyanide 3-chlorophenylhydrazone) from MilliporeSigma (cat. number C2759) for 24h. Lysates from HAP1 WT and *PINK1* KO treated or not with CCCP were prepared, and 30 μ g of protein were processed for Western Blot with the indicated Serine/threonine-protein kinase PINK1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab137361 at 1/1000, ab186303* at 1/1000, ab216144** at 1/1000, ab23707 at 1/1000, ab300623** at 1/1000, A7131 at 1/1000, BC100-494 at 1/1000, NBP2-36488* at 1/1000, 6946** at 1/1000, 23274-1-AP at 1/1000, MA5-11153* at 1/1000, PA5-13402 at 1/1000, and PA5-86941 at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 63 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 1: Serine/threonine-protein kinase PINK1 antibody screening by Western Blot

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All tested Serine/threonine-protein kinase PINK1 antibodies are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

Antibody screening by Western Blot

Western Blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. HAP1 WT and *PINK1* KO (listed in Table 1) were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number 78429). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and Western Blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western Blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau staining which is scanned to show together with individual Western Blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes are incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

References

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